

THE ROLE OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN MODERN ECONOMY

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Abstract.

The textile industry plays a crucial role in the modern economy, contributing significantly to global trade and employment. It is a major driver of economic growth, particularly in developing countries, where it serves as a source of foreign exchange and provides income for millions of people. The industry has become increasingly important due to the growth of fashion and retail markets, as well as the increased demand for sustainable and ethically-produced clothing.

Key words.

modern technology, the industrial revolution, manufacturing, automation of textile production, the textile industry.

The textile industry is an essential sector of the modern economy and plays a critical role in global trade and commerce. It is responsible for the manufacturing of fibers, yarns, fabrics, and finished products, such as clothing, household textiles, and industrial textiles. The industry employs a vast number of people globally, and its revenues represent a significant contribution to the GDP of many countries.

The textile industry's importance lies not only in its economic contributions but also in its role in the fashion industry. It is responsible for meeting the increasing demand for high-quality, inexpensive, and fashionable clothing globally. Moreover, with the rise in eco-friendly and sustainable fashion, the textile industry's importance has only increased.

The textile industry is also a source of innovation and technological advancement, with modern technology being applied to fabrics, textile processes, and automation. The industry is also responsible for sustainable and ethical production practices that promote transparency, fair labor standards, and sustainable sourcing of raw materials.

In summary, the textile industry is a crucial sector in the modern economy, contributing to employment, economic growth, innovation, and fashion trends.

The textile industry is one of the oldest industries in human history, with its roots dating back to prehistoric times. Early humans made their clothing by weaving natural fibers obtained from plants and animals. Over time, textiles became more complex, and the spinning wheel was invented, allowing for faster and higher quality production of textiles.

The Industrial Revolution in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries transformed the textile industry, as machines were developed that could spin and weave textiles on a massive scale. This led to the establishment of large-scale factories and mass production, leading to significant economic growth in Europe and North America. The invention of the cotton gin in 1793 revolutionized the processing of cotton, making it easier to produce cotton fabrics and significantly lowering the cost.

During the twentieth century, new synthetic fibers, such as nylon, rayon, and polyester, were developed, revolutionizing the textile industry and enabling the creation of new fabrics with unique properties. New technologies like computer-controlled weaving machines and robotics have further revolutionized the industry, improving efficiency rates and cleanliness in the production processes.

Today, the textile industry remains one of the largest and most important sectors of global manufacturing, with countries like China, India, Bangladesh, Vietnam, and Turkey being the largest producers. The industry continues to evolve, driven by changes in consumer demand, technological advancements, and sustainability concerns towards the environment.

The textile industry is a vast and complex sector that includes several sub-sectors involved in different stages of textile production, ranging from the manufacturing of fibers to the design, marketing, and distribution of finished textile products.

1. Manufacturing: The manufacturing sector involves the production of textile fibers, yarns, fabrics, and finished goods such as clothing, home furnishing, and industrial textiles. Textile manufacturers utilize different types of equipment, including spinning machines, weaving looms, dyeing machines, printing machines, cutting and sewing machines, and finishing machines. The manufacturing process may be done in-house, or outsourced to other facilities.

2. Design: The design sector is responsible for the creative aspects of the textile industry, including product design and development, textile engineering, and fashion trends forecasting. Fashion designers and textile engineers may work to create new fabrics, patterns, and styles that are appealing to consumers.

3. Marketing: The marketing sector involves promoting and selling textile products to wholesalers, retailers, and end-users. Textile marketers may develop advertising campaigns, create product displays, and negotiate contracts with distributors and retailers.

Technology plays a crucial role in the modern textile industry, particularly automation and machinery. Here are some ways that technology has impacted the industry:

1. Automation of textile production: Advances in automation technology have led to greater efficiency and speed in textile production. Robotic machinery can perform tasks such as spinning, weaving, and dyeing fabric, reducing the need for manual labor.

2. Digital textile printing: The introduction of digital textile printing technology has revolutionized the textile industry by enabling faster, more accurate printing of designs and patterns on fabric. Digital printing can be done on a range of fabrics such as cotton, silk, polyester, rayon, and more.

3. Smart textiles: Smart textiles contain technology that enables them to respond to the wearer's environment or interact with electronics. Examples of smart textiles include fabrics that can adjust their temperature, light up, or even charge a mobile device.

4. Sustainable textile production: Technology has helped make the textile industry more sustainable through innovations such as waterless dyeing techniques, recycled materials, and waste reduction technologies.

Globalization has had a significant impact on the textile industry through various factors including outsourcing, trade agreements, and competition.

Outsourcing: Globalization has enabled the textile industry to outsource production to countries with lower labor overheads, and costs, which inevitably resulted in job loss in developed countries that previously had an active textile industry.

Trade Agreements: Various trade agreements have been signed between countries to facilitate the exchange of goods and services. In textiles, these include free-trade agreements, tariff reductions, and multinational trade deals. However, while these agreements aim to facilitate trade-related activities, they can come at the cost of domestic production, particularly within the textile industry.

Competition: Due to the interconnectedness of the global market, the textile industry's competitive landscape has become more challenging. Manufacturers are competing with other companies from different regions that may offer better pricing, quality, and innovation. As a result, textile manufacturers are continually

striving to improve their products' quality and reduce production costs to remain competitive.

The textile industry is facing several challenges and opportunities in the areas of sustainability, ethical production, and innovation. Here are some of them:

1. Sustainability: The textile industry is one of the most polluting industries worldwide, responsible for a significant amount of greenhouse gas emissions, water pollution, and waste generation. Therefore, there is a growing need for sustainable production methods, including the use of organic and recycled fabrics, reduction of water consumption, and implementation of circular economy models to reduce waste.

2. Ethical Production: The textile industry has often been associated with exploitative labor practices and poor working conditions, especially in developing countries. Therefore, ethical production, which entails ensuring fair wages and safe working conditions for workers, has become a priority for many textile companies.

3. Innovation: Continuous innovation is essential in the textile industry to keep up with changing customer demands and preferences. With the advent of new technologies, textile companies can improve their production processes, create new products, and enhance their supply chain management.

Opportunities:

1. Consumer demand for sustainable and ethical products is growing rapidly and creating new opportunities for textile brands that prioritize these factors.

2. Technological advancements, such as 3D printing, smart textiles, and nanotechnology, can help textile companies create new products and enhance their production processes.

3. Increased interest in customization and personalization has created an opportunity for textile companies to offer made-to-measure clothing and other personalized products.

Challenges:

1. Implementing sustainable production methods can be challenging and costly for textile companies, particularly for smaller businesses.

2. Achieving ethical production requires collaboration among stakeholders, including suppliers, manufacturers, and retailers, which can be difficult to achieve.

3. Innovating in an industry that produces such a high volume of products can be challenging, especially considering the costs involved in researching and developing new products.

GLOBAL TEXTILE GROUP is a bright representative of a technological textile company built like a cluster in Uzbekistan.

The group of companies includes manufacturing enterprises that carry out all stages of processing raw materials: from growing cotton to the production of finished textile products.

The GLOBAL TEXTILE GROUP includes several spinning factories, knitting, dyeing workshops located in Tashkent and Fergana, a cotton gin, as well as its own cotton fields with an introduced drip irrigation system.

Today GLOBAL TEXTILE GROUP produces the following types of products:

- dyed knitted fabrics with or without lycra and polyester
- carded yarn
- compact combed yarn
- mixed yarn.

Plants, factories and workshops of GLOBAL TEXTILE GROUP are equipped with the most modern equipment of the world's leading manufacturers: Lummus (USA), Rieter (Switzerland), Mayer & Cie (Germany), Thies (Germany), Santex (Switzerland), Mario Crosta (Italy), Ferarro (Italy), Corino (Italy), Xetma (Germany), Odesi (Turkey), Bahar (Turkey), James Heal (UK), Uster (Switzerland) and others.

The quality of products, environmental friendliness of production and compliance with international standards of social responsibility are confirmed by all the necessary international certificates:

- ISO 9001 certified
- OEKO-TEX
- Compact4Compact
- USTERIZED
- SEDEX
- BSCI

Today, GLOBAL TEXTILE GROUP successfully exports its products to the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, Bangladesh, Turkey, China, the Russian Federation, and also sells it on the local market.

The textile industry is projected to experience significant growth and expansion in the foreseeable future, driven mainly by increasing consumer demand, technological advancements, and emerging markets.

One of the key drivers of growth in the textile industry is the rising demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products. Consumers are becoming increasingly aware of the impact of the textile industry on the environment and are demanding more sustainable options. As a result, we are seeing an increase in the production of organic cotton, recycled polyester, and other eco-friendly materials.

Another factor contributing to the growth of the textile industry is the rapid technological advancements being made in the industry. For example, 3D printing technology is being used to create clothing and textiles in completely new and innovative ways. We are also seeing the emergence of smart textiles, which incorporate technology and sensors to create new and useful functionalities.

In terms of the expansion of the textile industry in emerging markets, there is a significant potential for growth. Emerging markets such as India, China, Vietnam, and Bangladesh are already major textile producers and exporters, and their economies are rapidly growing. As per a report published by ResearchAndMarkets, the global textile market value is expected to reach \$1.5 trillion USD by 2025, with emerging markets like Asia-Pacific contributing to a significant portion of this growth.

However, the textile industry also faces challenges such as supply chain disruptions, labor compliance, trade wars, and uncertainty in the world economy. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated these challenges, leading to factory closures, canceled orders, and a decline in demand.

Overall, while there are still uncertainties and challenges facing the textile industry, there is significant potential for growth and expansion in emerging markets. The industry's ability to adapt to the changing consumer demands and technological advancements will play a significant role in determining its future success.

In summary, the textile industry is a multifaceted sector that includes manufacturing, design, and marketing subsectors. Manufacturers produce textile products, designers create innovative designs and predict industry trends, while marketers promote and sell products to wholesalers, retailers, and consumers. Technology has had a significant impact on the modern textile industry, making textile production more efficient, sustainable, and innovative. Globalization has had a substantial effect on the textile industry through various impacts such as outsourcing, trade agreements, and competition. To remain competitive, textile manufacturers need to continually invest in technology and innovation and adapt to emerging trends and patterns.

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